

PERFORMANCE OF PIANO TRILLS: EFFECTS OF HANDS, FINGERS, NOTES AND EMOTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Trill is a type of musical ornament. In automatic playback of piano music scores, trills are usually synthesised as a sequence of repeated notes with equal duration and dynamic level. This is not how trills are performed by pianists. In this study, trills were performed by three pianists on a Yamaha Disklavier and recorded as both audio and MIDI files. Then note duration, inter-onset interval (IOI) and key velocity for each note were extracted from Midi files and analyzed in relation to hands, notes and emotions. Four significant effects were found; 1) hand effect: trills on right hand were in average performed with a faster rate, shorter note duration, longer off duration and faster key velocity, 2) finger effect: within the two notes forming a trill, notes with lower fingering number were performed with shorter off duration, while keeping note duration and key velocity close, 3) emotion effect: emotion mainly contributed to dynamic level, 4) crescendo effect: when crescendo happened, note duration and off duration compensated with each other and kept IOI at a almost constant value.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the development of acoustic analysis technology, researchers started to explore the characteristics of musical performance quantitatively. Various parameters (e.g. inter-onset intervals, loudness levels, note duration, etc.) are used to model different aspects of expressive musical performance. Some of the models are more descriptive than quantitative, and some other models focus more on specific aspects [1]. This project mainly focuses on descriptive piano trills modeling.

Trill is a type of musical ornaments, which "requires one of the fastest alternating movements of which the hand is capable" [2] in piano performance. It is an expressive component in piano performance which has been derived from *tremolo* in the XVII century. However, it is still a problem in synthesizing piano trills for music score playback. Depending on the capability of hand as well as mass and dimension difference between each finger, trill is not a combination of fast notes with equal duration and dynamic level, but contains many variations. There are similar patterns of ornaments in other forms of musical performance,

for example stringed instruments and singing, which is called vibrato or trill. Both qualitative and quantitative characteristics of vibrato have been studied for decades. In 1990, [3] assessed trill rates of nine professional early music singers and found slow trill rates ranged from 2.0 to 6.9 Hz and fast trill rates ranged from 7.5 to 12.4 Hz. In 1994, [4] measured vibrato rate for ten singers singing Schubert's Ave Maria. He found the vibrato rate increased at the end of each tone, which was also verified to exist in stringed instruments as well. In 2004, [5] analyzed *tremolo*, trill and vibrato rate for 56 string players. He found ornaments on low notes were performed slower and player with more advanced skills can perform faster. Besides, mean rates for slow, medium and fast tempo are 6.4, 9.3 and 12.1 Hz respectively. These studies above mainly focus on vibrato rate and other qualitative parameters, and there are also other work developing comprehensive computation model for vibrato performance. Schoonderwaldt and Friberg [6] modeled violin vibrato with rate, extent and sound level envelopes, using the method of analysis-by-synthesis approach.

Different from most of the other studies which focused on the temporal aspects of trills, Moore [2] analyzed both on-off timing and dynamic level of notes in piano trills. In his study, trills were recorded by using one of the first Yamaha Disklavier models (a Grand Piano Model C3 equipped with a MIDI interface). Fingers movements and electromyographic (EMG) were monitored at the same time. Four subjects were required to perform a trill exercise consisting of D4 and E4, and also a passage of musical passage from the first movement of the Beethoven Piano Concerto No. 1, which included trills with note pairs D5/E5 and D5#/E5. As a result, average trill rate was 12 Hz; note duration differed by less than 1 ms for D4 and E4; average dynamic level differed by less than 2 MIDI units between D4 and E4, which was less than variation within note D4 or E4; and the greatest performance difference was the gap between offset to onset of next note, in which average gap between offset of D4 to onset of E4 was 17 ms while the average gap from E4 to D4 was 24 ms; also it was observed that increases in key velocity led to increases in note duration. Similar results were observed for note pairs D5/E5 and D5#/E5.

Besides the playing techniques, also the emotional expression used by pianists can have an effect on the performance of trills. Emotion in music can be communicated in terms of variations of a number of parameters such as note height, intensity, duration, articulation, sound level, attach

speed [7,8]. Therefore, since note duration and sound level are two of the main expressive parameters in piano performance, in this study we will also investigate how emotional expression can influence the performance of trills. This study focuses on both temporal and dynamic aspects of piano trills in relation to hands, pitches and emotions. The trills considered in this study are continuous trills that extend over several bars.

2. EXPERIMENT

Three right-handed young pianists (2F, 1M; average age 21.7, SD 3.5), from the master programme in Classical Music Performance at the Royal College of Music in Stockholm, were recruited as participants for the experiment. They have been playing piano for 13 years in average (SD 5.2). The experiment consisted of 3 parts: 1) performance practice, 2) performance recording, and 3) post-interview about the performances. JS Bach composition Invention in D minor BWV 775¹ was chosen to be the experiment material because of its relatively long trills to be played by both hands (three bars for right hand, and five bars for left hand).

In part 1, the experimenter sent out the score to the participants so the participants could get enough time to practise and be able to perform the piece fluently. The instructions and consent forms were also sent together with the score. In part 2, the participants were asked to come to the experiment location and produce performances in the following 6 conditions:

1. Please perform the piece in your own interpretation as in a concert.
2. Please perform the piece in the same way as in task 1 without trills, which means hold the beginning note of trill until the end of trill.
3. Please perform the piece in exaggerated happy emotion.
4. Please perform the piece in the same emotion as in task 3 without trills, which means hold the beginning note of trill until the end of trill.
5. Please perform the piece in exaggerated sad emotion.
6. Please perform the piece in the same emotion as in task 5 without trills, which means hold the beginning note of trill until the end of trill.

The participants were allowed to play in each condition as many times as they wanted, which resulted in a set of performance recordings, until they felt satisfied with the recording. The pianists did not make use of the piano pedals in their performances. After finishing performance under each condition, participants were asked to indicate the best performance recording, which would be used later in data analysis. This means that for each pianist only one of

the performances made with the same expressive intention was kept for the analysis.

This study mainly focused on trill performance, so only data collected under condition 1, 3 and 5 were analyzed later. The performances were played on a YAMAHA Disklavier E3, and automatically stored in MIDI format using the control unit available on the Disklavier. Stereo audio recordings of the performances were also made using a sound card (RME Babyface) connected to a MacBook Pro laptop computer (all recorded data are freely available online²). In part 3 of the experiment, participants were interviewed about their technique when playing trills in different conditions, and about their overall experience during the experiment.

3. RESULTS

The MIDI Toolbox 1.1 [9] was used for analyzing the MIDI recordings. Onset time, duration, dynamic and note number of each performed note were extracted. In MIDI format, dynamic is given by MIDI velocity (0..127) and note is given by MIDI note number (0..127). The MIDI note numbers of the trill in the score were respectively, 52 (E3, 164.81 Hz) and 53 (F3, 174.61 Hz) for the trill played by the left hand, and 72 (C5, 523.25 Hz) and 74 (D5, 587.33 Hz) for the right hand. All trills were extracted. As described in the experiment instructions, participants were asked to play the piece in three different expressions, including sad emotion, happy emotion and the emotional expression they would use when performing the piece in concert, which is called "concert emotion" in the following. Trill rate, inter-onset interval (IOI), note duration, off-duration and MIDI velocity were taken as dependent variables. Trill rate refers to number of notes played per second. IOI refers to the time between the onset time of one note and that of the next note. Trill rate was calculated by dividing the number of notes by the duration of the trill passage. Off-duration refers to the time interval between the time when a key is released and the onset time of the next note. Larger off-duration values indicate longer break (also called Key-Detached Time, KDT, see [10]) between finger switch in trills, which corresponds to a more *staccato* trill. On the contrary, shorter off-duration time value indicates shorter break, and when it has a negative value, adjacent notes are overlapping (also called Key-Overlap-Time, KOT, see [10]), resulting in a more *legato* trill. Hand (left or right), note and emotion were taken as independent variables. Hand refers to which hand played the trill. After Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test, trill rate was shown to be approximately normally distributed, while IOI, note duration, off-duration and MIDI velocity failed the test. Therefore, when examining correlations, Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation test was used for trill rate and Spearman Rank-Order Correlation test was used for other variables.

¹ <https://ndmusicedition.files.wordpress.com/2011/01/inventions-largerspacing-4.pdf>

² <https://kth.box.com/v/nsmc2019trills>

3.1 Hand Effect

3.1.1 Trill Rate

The mean for trill rate was 10.1 note/s and the standard deviation was 1.5 note/s regardless of hand. Results showed that trill rate and hand were significantly correlated ($p = .002 < 0.05$) and right hand had higher trill rate (see Table 1).

Table 1: Means and standard deviations of trill rate on each hand

Hand	M (note/s)	SD(note/s)
Left	9.1	0.4
Right	11.1	1.4

Table 2: Means and standard deviations of IOI on each hand

Hand	M (ms)	SD (ms)
Left	108.56	17.34
Right	93.44	28.08

3.1.2 Note Duration

There was a negative correlation between note duration and hand, which was statistically significant ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$) (see and Table 3).

Table 3: Means and standard deviations of note duration on each hand

Hand	M (ms)	SD (ms)
Left	89.94	22.90
Right	64.96	26.60

3.1.3 Off-Duration

Hand and off.duration were significantly correlated ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$). Notes in trills played by the right hand had longer off-duration than thoes performed by the left hand (see Table 4).

Table 4: Means and standard deviations of off duration on each hand

Hand	M (ms)	SD (ms)
Left	18.62	25.31
Right	28.49	18.63

3.1.4 Key Velocity

A significant positive correlation was found between Key velocity and hand ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$) (see Table 5).

3.2 Note Effect

Since hand effect was significant to all dependent variables, data were grouped by hand in the following analysis.

Table 5: Means and standard deviations of key velocity on each hand. Values are expressed in MIDI velocity values, which vary between 0 = *silentnote* and 127 = *loudestsoundlevelpossible*

Hand	M	SD
Left	55.84	6.99
Right	61.33	6.40

3.2.1 IOI

For left hand, IOI and note were significantly correlated ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$) and IOI from lower note to higher note was longer than the opposite (see Table 6).

Table 6: Means and standard deviations of IOI for each note on left hand

Note	M (ms)	SD (ms)
E3	116.70	13.40
F3	100.11	16.95

For right hand, IOI and note were also significantly correlated ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$) and IOI from higher notes to lower notes was longer than the opposite (see Table 7).

Table 7: Means and standard deviations of IOI for each note on right hand

Note	M (ms)	SD (ms)
C5	83.94	29.21
D5	102.81	23.50

3.2.2 Note Duration

A significant positive correlation between note duration and note was found for the left hand ($p = 0.007 < 0.05$), but not for the right hand (see Table 8).

Table 8: Means and standard deviations of note duration for each notes on left hand

Note	M (ms)	SD (ms)
E3	86.66	22.48
F3	93.35	22.90

3.2.3 Off-Duration

For left hand, when checking correlation between off duration and note, trill data showed significant correlation between off-duration and note ($p = .000$). Off-duration was longer when playing from lower to higher note than from higher to lower note (see Table 9).

For right hand, the correlation between note and off duration was also significant ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$) and it took longer to switch from higher notes to lower notes (see and Table 10).

Table 9: Means and standard deviations of off duration for each pitch on left hand

Note	M (ms)	SD (ms)
E3	30.04	22.50
F3	6.76	22.50

Table 10: Means and standard deviations of off duration for each note on right hand

Note	M (ms)	SD (ms)
C5	19.18	16.58
D5	37.66	15.93

3.2.4 Key velocity

For the right hand, note and key velocity show a positive significant correlation ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$) (see Table 11), but not for the left hand.

Table 11: Means and standard deviations of key velocity for each note on right hand

Note	M	SD
C5	59.70	5.68
D5	62.93	6.68

3.3 Emotion Effect

3.3.1 Trill Rate

Trill rate and emotion are not significantly correlated for either hand ($p = .535 > 0.05, p = .874 > 0.05$) (see Tables 12 and 13). Still it is possible to observe a tendency for slower rate for the sad performances compared to the faster rates of the happy and concert ones.

Table 12: Means and standard deviations of trill rate for each emotion on left hand

Emotion	M (note/s)	SD (note/s)
Sad	8.99	0.42
Concert	9.21	0.56
Happy	9.23	0.46

Table 13: Means and standard deviations of trill rate for each emotion on right hand

Emotion	M (note/s)	SD (note/s)
Sad	10.70	1.67
Concert	11.62	1.28
Happy	10.91	1.88

3.3.2 IOI

Since IOI was found to be significantly correlated to hand and note, the data were grouped by hand and pitch for variable control. For left hand, IOI shows a significant correlation with emotion for the left hand and note E3 only

($p = 0.042 < 0.05$) (see Table 14). No significant correlation was observed for the notes played by the right hand.

Table 14: Means and standard deviations of IOI for each emotion on note E3

Emotion	M (ms)	SD (ms)
Sad	120.31	13.66
Concert	113.99	13.05
Happy	115.79	12.82

For right hand, IOI had no significant correlation with emotion on either note.

3.3.3 Off-Duration

Since off duration was found to be significantly correlated with note for both hands, off duration data was grouped by pitch during analysis. For the right hand, the correlation between off duration and emotion was found significant only for note D5 ($p = 0.019 < 0.05$) (see Table 15).

Table 15: Means and standard deviations of off duration for each emotion on pitch D5

Emotion	M (ms)	SD (ms)
Sad	41.06	13.56
Concert	38.51	12.47
Happy	33.28	20.05

3.3.4 Key Velocity

Significant positive correlations between emotion and key velocity was found for all the notes played by both left ($p = 0.005 < 0.05$) (see Table 16) and right hands ($p = 0.001 < 0.05, p = 0.000 < 0.05$) (see Tables 17 and 18).

Table 16: Means and standard deviations of key velocity for each emotion on left hand

Emotion	M	SD
Sad	54.85	7.25
Concert	55.53	6.57
Happy	57.20	6.97

Table 17: Means and standard deviations of key velocity for each emotion on note C5

Emotion	M	SD
Sad	58.04	5.90
Concert	59.28	4.54
Happy	61.88	5.95

3.4 Crescendo Effect

From the post-experiment interview, it emerged that pianist 2 intended to do a crescendo in trills. Therefore the effect of crescendo was analyzed for all three pianists.

Table 18: Means and standard deviations of key velocity for each emotion on note D5

Emotion	M	SD
Sad	59.85	7.41
Concert	62.41	5.47
Happy	66.64	5.04

3.4.1 Key Velocity

From the analysis of key velocity values of the trills performed by the three pianists, we found that pianists 1 and 2 performed a crescendo with their left hand (see Figure 1).

3.4.2 IOI

IOI did not show any obvious tendency when plotted with time (See Figure 2), and it was kept almost constant throughout the trill.

3.4.3 Note Duration and Off-Duration

Note duration increased (See Figure 3) during the performance of trills, and as a consequence off-duration symmetrically decreased with time (See Figure 4).

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Hand Effect

Humans have usually a dominant hand which can perform a better, faster and more precise task than the other hand. Non-dominant hand can also be trained to improve, however, skills asymmetry still exists for professional musicians [11]. In this study, handing effect was significant to trill rate, IOI, note duration, off-duration and key velocity. Compared to left hand, right hand had higher trill rate. The difference of trill rate between left hand and right hand was approximately 2 note/s. Right hand also had shorter IOI and note duration in average, which is reasonable because these enabled a faster trill rate. However, right hand had longer off-duration. This indicates that pianists performed on average more *staccato* with the right hand than with left hand, and that they had more time for preparing for the next note to be played in the trill. Meanwhile, right hand had higher key velocity, made possible by a more *legato* performance.

To sum it up, trills on right hand had faster trill rate, shorter off note duration, longer off duration and higher key velocity while keeping note duration as consistent as possible.

4.2 Note Effect

Note effect was significant to IOI, off duration for both hands, note duration for left hand and key velocity for right hand. Note effect can also be treated as fingering effect. For left hand, higher note was played by a finger with lower fingering number (lower finger). On the contrary, for right hand higher note is played by a finger with higher fingering number (higher finger). In the results, higher note for left hand and lower note for right hand had shorter IOI, which also indicated that lower finger for both hands had

shorter IOI. With the same analysis, it was easy to find that lower finger also had shorter off duration. This finding was corresponding with Moore's study [2]. He found that the greatest performance difference between fingers was "the gap between the end of one note and the onset of next". Although note effect was significant to note duration for left hand, the mean difference between notes was approximately 7 ms, which was much smaller than standard deviation values of note duration. Similarly, the mean difference of key velocity between notes was approximately 3, which was also smaller than standard deviation values.

In the analysis above, IOI and off duration were shorter for lower finger. At the same time, note duration was either not significantly affected by note or the mean value difference between notes was very small. Since IOI is the sum of note duration and off-duration, off-duration is possibly the main contribution factor to the difference of IOI between notes. Also, pianists 1 and 2 started from the upper note in the trill performed by the right hand, while pianist 3 from the lower note.

In summary, within 2 notes forming the trill, notes with lower fingering were performed with shorter off-duration, while keeping note duration and key velocity almost at constant values.

4.3 Emotion Effect

Emotion effect was significant to key velocity. For note E3 on left hand, emotion effect was also significant. However the mean differences between different emotions was smaller than the standard deviation values. This result indicated that emotion effect mainly contributed to dynamic level but not temporal aspect of the trill passages and happy emotion resulted in higher dynamic level. This is reasonable since because of the high speed at which notes in trills are performed, it is easier for the pianist to control the sound level than the duration of the already very short notes.

4.4 Crescendo Effect

With *crescendo* in trill passage, key velocity and note duration increased with time, while off-duration decreased. Besides, IOI values did not show any obvious tendency. In conclusion, when *crescendo* happened, note duration and off-duration compensated with each other and kept IOI at almost constant value.

5. CONCLUSION

By implementing the experiment and analyzing recordings from the experiment, the main findings are listed below:

1. Hand effect: Trills on right hand have faster trill rate, shorter note duration, longer off duration and higher key velocity while keeping note duration almost constant.
2. Note effect: Within the two notes forming the trill, notes with lower fingering have shorter off-duration, while keeping note duration and key velocity close.

Figure 1: Plot of key velocity vs onset time for each note in the trills played by the three pianists

Figure 2: Plot of IOI for the trill played with the left hand by pianists 1 and 2.

3. Emotion effect: Emotion mainly contributed to dynamic level and happy emotion resulted in higher dynamic level, compared to sad emotion
4. Crescendo effect: In trills with crescendo, note duration and off-duration compensate each other and IOI is therefore kept at almost constant value.

These findings cover both temporal aspects and dynamic level of a trill. They can provide qualitative constraints for trill performance modelling. However, there are also limitations in this experiment. Firstly, there were only three pianists that participated in the experiments which was a small sample size. Secondly, the piano skills to these three pianists as well as their performance style varied which lead to slightly different performances. Nevertheless it was possible to observe significant effects in the performance

of trills, probably because of the high speed at which they are played. For future study, it will be interesting to verify the conclusions with more pianists, different compositions and tempi. Also, analysis of commercial recordings of the same and similar pieces will be conducted. The final results will hopefully lead to even more strong conclusions, which will help to implement a rule for the automatic expressive performance of piano trills at least of the Baroque repertoire.

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Figure 3: Plot of note duration to onset time for each pianist

Figure 4: Plot of off duration to onset time for each pianist

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³ <http://www.kth.se/navet>